

INTEGRATING ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP) METHODOLOGIES INTO CLASSROOM-BASED TEACHING.

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Abstract

This study explores the integration of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) methodologies into classroom-based teaching, with a focus on English for Medical Purposes (EMP). The main aim is to evaluate the effectiveness of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and communicative approaches in developing students' professional language skills. The research is based on ESP course design principles proposed by Woodrow (2018), as well as comparative analysis of Business and Aviation English courses. These approaches emphasize authentic materials, task-based learning, and real-life communication. The methodology involves the application of PBL through case studies, group discussions, and simulation of patient-doctor interactions. Students actively participate in solving real-life medical problems, while the teacher acts as a facilitator. The results show that ESP methodologies significantly improve students' speaking skills, use of medical terminology, and confidence in professional communication. Additionally, learners develop critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. The study concludes that integrating ESP methodologies into medical English teaching creates an effective learner-centered environment and better prepares students for real-world professional communication.

Keywords: ESP, Medical English, Problem-Based Learning, Communicative Approach, EFL

To develop this project, I have clearly analyzed how Woodrow (2018) addressed ESP course introduction part and what elements she emphasized to create specific ESP project. I have selected English for Medical Purposes course for second-year students for this project. It mostly includes academic skills as well as workplace requirements. From the Part 3 of Woodrow's (2018) examples, I have outlined students and professionals needs for learning subject, and terminologies, also I addressed what are the issues of patient-doctor interaction.

I have selected "Programme for Business English majors" by Zuocheng Zhang (2017) and "Airport English" by Joan Cutting (2017) for this project, Medical English for the ESP context. However, I have chosen medical English as an ESP context, Business and Aviation English have approaches which mostly emphasize real communicative situations

They highlight original materials, activities and most importantly speaking interaction for target learners.

Firstly, in the first article Project-based learning is considered as a main method. Since this method is oriented real-life situations and problem-solving techniques, it can be beneficial for Medical students. Moreover, according to Zhang, Z. (2017) business English students promote critical and creative thinking

in the process of learning English Language (p.244). Also, medical students are demanded to critically analyze patients' diseases or diagnosis. So, language serves as an assistance to solve such problems by communicating international doctors. English serves as a lingua franca for Business people, because they have to communicate with many people from different countries. From these perspectives, medical students should use at least medium English to interact with international medical students or doctors. Secondly, communicative and task-based approaches are prioritized throughout the article. In aviation sphere, students do real-life tasks and language learning happens throughout the process. They should learn some terminologies related to their job. Additionally, they are demanded to learn language to express their ideas in urgent situations. So, it fits really for medical students, as they also should learn terminologies, specific vocabularies in medical sphere.

I will use both approaches for my target learners, because both include real life situations and practical usage of English language. Additionally, PBL is directed to investigating critically, while Task-based approach focuses on communication, which means thoroughly reflection of medical students' needs.

To design my ESP course for Medical practitioners, I want to choose Problem-based learning approach. PBL is connected to medical sphere as it involves real-life problems. Woodrow (2018) states that "learning occurs during the process of investigating and producing a solution to a problem, thanks to PBL" (p.131). Moreover, using PBL in Medical-based ESP context will be advantageous for the students, because they will be familiar with methodology related to their discipline. If students have any problems, they will do researches to find proper solution. In that situation PBL comes to help for students.

Using PBL in my course design will be useful for my students, because it centralizes the students themselves. It means that teacher is considered as a facilitator and students are demanded to be independently solve problems by critical thinking and authentic task performance. In PBL approach, students can find one possible solution, for example identification of disease or treatment. In PBL students are expected to work on groups and research diagnosis, and they are required to decide on the disease according to their own research in the field.

While preparing course design English for Medical students, I learned a lot of important points about how to take into consideration students' needs, interest, workplace needs and requirements. Most of my students have interest to learn the language, because they can easily communicate with international doctors by using medical terminologies, specific vocabularies and methods. To prepare effective course design, teacher should think about genres which learners are related to specific discourse community. Viana et al. (2019) mentioned that "using genres effectively shows professionals' ability in the discourse communities which they belong to" (p.21). It means that professional usage of those genres shows how that person is knowledgeable or skillful in terms of his/her field.

To strength my work, I addressed some course examples from Woodrow's (2018) Part 3 articles. For example, I adapted task-based approach and communicative competence, because they should learn how to find a solution in real-life problematic situations. By using these methods, learners can be proficient on, for example, patient-doctor interactions, explaining treatment and diagnosing the patient. Moreover, according to Belcher (2006) ESP practitioners should prepare materials by using wide angle approach to avoid limited field-specific knowledge. Specific knowledge makes students perfect.

Medical students should be aware of real-life situations, so that reason it will be good if teacher uses authentic materials. I took authentic materials directly from hospitals, I recorded some conversations and I take some articles from WHO (World Health Organizations). Johns and Dudley (1991) stated that materials and activities should be selected carefully for specific group of learners. It means that teachers take in to consideration the authenticity.

As an ESP teacher, I have learnt how to prepare course design with specific objectives which actually meet the students needs. I tried to find my students weakness, by using diagnostic tests or formatives as I mentioned above, and help them to overcome difficulty to learn the language. While assessing, I have included their results and participation during the lesson.

Overall, this project greatly helped me to design creative and engaged course design for my medical students for now and for future. I have learnt mistakes I did before, for example, using ready-made materials always not a good way of teaching. Because they should feel themselves in real-life situations.

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